

Autocorrelation Features for Synthetic Aperture Sonar Image Seabed Segmentation

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Abstract—High-resolution synthetic aperture sonar (SAS) systems yield richly detailed images of seabed environments. Algorithms that automatically segment and label seabed textures such as coral, sea grass, sand ripple, and mud, require suitable features that discriminate between the texture classes. Here we present a robust, parameterized SAS image texture model based on the autocorrelation function (ACF) of the intensity image. This ACF texture model has been shown to accurately model first- and second-order statistical features of various seabed environments. An unsupervised multi-class k -means segmentation algorithm that uses the features derived from the ACF model is employed to label rock and ripple textures from a set of textured SAS images. The results of the segmentation are compared against the performance of the segmentation approach using biorthogonal wavelets and Haralick features. In the described experiments, the ACF model features are shown to produce better segmentations than the features based on wavelet coefficients and Haralick features for classifiers of low complexity.

Index Terms—Autocorrelation, expectation-maximization algorithm, image segmentation, synthetic aperture sonar, wavelet coefficients.

I. INTRODUCTION

In the past ten years a sonar sensing approach known as stripmap synthetic aperture sonar (SAS) has matured to the point where autonomous underwater vehicles carrying these systems can produce highly-resolved seabed images. These images clearly depict sand ripples, sea grass beds, and rock and coral beds in near photographic clarity. Figure 1 shows a montage of various synthetic aperture sonar images of the seabed containing different seabed textures. Algorithms that segment and label these textured regions are useful for higher level automated tasks such as scene recognition, data mining from previously surveyed data, and seabed mapping. In this research we propose a set of image segmentation features based on the autocorrelation function (ACF) of the SAS intensity image and compare unsupervised segmentation results using the ACF features against recently proposed features based on wavelet coefficients and the gray-level co-occurrence matrix, also known as Haralick features..

Several methods for unsupervised sonar image texture segmentation have recently been proposed. In all of the methods discussed here, features are first extracted from a block of pixels in the image prior to performing segmentation. Various authors have built upon the unsupervised texture segmentation scheme of Jain and Farrokhnia, where coefficients from Gabor filter banks are used as features for a k -means segmentation al-

Fig. 1: Montage of SAS sample images with various textures. Sand ripples of various sizes and periodicities, sea grass, hard-packed sand, and rock beds are all visible in these images.

gorithm [1]. In [2] Williams used coefficients from a biorthogonal wavelet decomposition to segment rippled and rocky seabed textures. The coefficients were then comparatively segmented using spectral clustering and k -means clustering. Lianantonakis and Petillot used Haralick features and Chan-Vese active contours to segment sand ripple and rocky regions from hard-pack sand and other textures [3]. Samiee and Rad combined the approaches of Jain, Farrokhnia, Lianantonakis, and Petillot, using Gabor filter bank coefficients and Chan-Vese active contours to segment seabed textures [4].

In this paper, we compare SAS image segmentation results using texture features from a parameterized two-dimensional SAS image pixel intensity ACF model with two other approaches from [2] and [3] that use features based on bi-orthogonal wavelet coefficients and Haralick features, respectively. Features are extracted using the various methods and an unsupervised k -means segmentation algorithm is used to assign labels. Segmentation results are compared between the various

methods based on both average correct classification rates. An analysis of the the multimodality of the texture feature space is also conducted to infer supervised classification performance amongst the three feature sets.

The outline of the remaining paper follows. In Section II we describe the ACF texture model and the texture parameter estimation procedure. In Section III we describe the segmentation algorithm and the three feature extraction methods based on the ACF texture model, biorthogonal wavelet coefficients, and the gray-level co-occurrence matrix, respectively. In Section IV we present segmentation results for the three feature extraction methods on textured seabed images and compare the approaches. In Section V we review the findings.

II. TEXTURE FEATURE EXTRACTION USING AUTOCORRELATION FUNCTION PARAMETERS

Expanding upon previous work by Oliver [5], [6], Cobb, et al. presented a parameterized ACF model to extract texture features from SAS intensity images [7]. This model was shown to fit various synthesized textures as well as sand, sea grass, and rock textures in real SAS images. Recently the ACF model was extended to properly fit periodic textures such as rippled seabed in [8]. In simplest terms the model fits the surface of the two-dimensional ACF of an intensity image patch or window, where intensity is defined as the squared-magnitude (or energy) value of an image pixel. The intensity ACF model (normalized by the intensity image mean μ_I) is defined for ACF spatial lags X and Y as

$$R_{IN} \triangleq \frac{R_I}{\mu_I} - 1 = R_h^2 + \frac{1}{\nu} \sum_i \eta_i l_{x_i} l_{y_i} |\Sigma_i|^{-\frac{1}{2}} \cdot \left[e^{-\frac{1}{2} \cdot [\bar{X} \ \bar{Y}] \Sigma_i^{-1} [\bar{X} \ \bar{Y}]^T} + R_h^2 \right]. \quad (1)$$

where $[\bar{X} \ \bar{Y}] = [X \ Y] - [\mu_{X_i} \ \mu_{Y_i}]$, μ_{X_i} is the mean of the i^{th} mixture component in the X spatial lag direction, μ_{Y_i} is the mean of the i^{th} mixture component in the Y spatial lag direction, $R_h(X, Y)$ is the ACF of the imaging point spread function imposed by the beam former or image formation algorithm and is defined as

$$R_h(X, Y) \triangleq e^{-\frac{1}{8} \cdot [X \ Y] B^{-1} [X \ Y]^T}, \quad (2)$$

where

$$B = \begin{bmatrix} \beta_x^2 & 0 \\ 0 & \beta_y^2 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (3)$$

ν is the shape parameter of the single-point image statistics (here we assume intensity pixels are K -distributed [9]), η_i is mixture parameter corresponding to the spatial correlation parameters l_{x_i} and l_{y_i} , and Σ_i is composed of a rotation matrix

$$\Psi_i = \begin{bmatrix} \cos \theta_i & \sin \theta_i \\ -\sin \theta_i & \cos \theta_i \end{bmatrix}, \quad (4)$$

a diagonal spatial correlation parameter matrix

$$\Lambda_i = \begin{bmatrix} l_{x_i}^2 & 0 \\ 0 & l_{y_i}^2 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (5)$$

and the imaging point spread function parameter matrix B via the following equation

$$\Sigma_i = \Psi_i (\Lambda_i + 2B) \Psi_i^T. \quad (6)$$

The mixing parameter is constrained such that $\sum_i \eta_i = 1$. The derivation of Equation (1) for zero-mean components is fully explained in [7], an extension of the derivation to nonzero-mean components is detailed in [8].

A. ACF Model Parameter Estimation

The ACF model parameter estimation algorithm assumes that estimates are available for the intensity ACF \hat{R}_I from an image block or window, the mean intensity $\hat{\mu}_I$, the imaging point spread function parameters $\hat{\beta}_x$ and $\hat{\beta}_y$ estimated via least-squares fit of the imaging point spread function [7], and $\hat{\nu}$ the single-point K -distribution shape parameter found using Raghavan's method [10] or another suitable method. With these estimates as inputs or knowns the remaining parameters l_{x_i} , l_{y_i} , $[\mu_{X_i} \ \mu_{Y_i}]$, θ_i , η_i , $i = \{1, 2, \dots, M\}$ from (1) are estimated by manipulating the intensity ACF equation into

$$\hat{R}_{IN}^{(k)} - \hat{R}_h^2 \left[1 + \frac{1}{\hat{\nu}} f(\eta_i^{(k-1)}, l_{x_i}^{(k-1)}, l_{y_i}^{(k-1)}) \right] = \frac{1}{\hat{\nu}} f(\eta_i^{(k)}, l_{x_i}^{(k)}, l_{y_i}^{(k)}) \cdot e^{-\frac{1}{2} \cdot [\bar{X} \ \bar{Y}] \Sigma_i^{-1} [\bar{X} \ \bar{Y}]^T}, \quad (7)$$

where

$$f(\eta_i, l_{x_i}, l_{y_i}) \triangleq \sum_i \eta_i \cdot l_{x_i} l_{y_i} |\Sigma_i|^{-\frac{1}{2}}.$$

The reader should notice that the right hand side of Equation (7) is a scaled M -component Gaussian mixture model of the form

$$C \cdot \sum_{i=1}^M \alpha_i G_i([\mu_{X_i} \ \mu_{Y_i}], \Sigma_i) \quad (8)$$

where

$$C = 2\pi \cdot \frac{\sum_j \eta_j l_{x_j} l_{y_j}}{\hat{\nu}} \quad (9)$$

and

$$\alpha_i = \frac{\eta_i \cdot l_{x_i} \cdot l_{y_i}}{\sum_j \eta_j l_{x_j} l_{y_j}}, \quad (10)$$

so that $\sum_i \alpha_i = 1$ and

$$G_i([\mu_{X_i} \ \mu_{Y_i}], \Sigma_i) = (2\pi)^{-1} |\Sigma_i|^{-\frac{1}{2}} e^{-\frac{1}{2} [\bar{X} \ \bar{Y}] \Sigma_i^{-1} [\bar{X} \ \bar{Y}]^T}. \quad (11)$$

Using the EM algorithm for truncated two-dimensional Gaussian mixture models described in [11]–[13], the parameters $\Theta_i = \{\alpha_i, \mu_{X_i}, \mu_{Y_i}, \Sigma_i\}$, $i = 1, \dots, M$, at step k are found by maximizing the likelihood function

$$L(\Theta^{(k)}) = \sum_{X, Y} \mathbf{g}^{(k)}(X, Y) \cdot \ln C^{(k)} \cdot \sum_{i=1}^M \alpha_i^{(k)} G_i^{(k)}(\Theta_i^{(k)}) \quad (12)$$

where

$$\mathbf{g}^{(k)}(X, Y) = \frac{\hat{R}_I}{\hat{\mu}_I} - 1 - \hat{R}_h^2 \cdot \left[1 + \frac{1}{\hat{\nu}} f(\eta_i^{(k-1)}, l_{x_i}^{(k-1)}, l_{y_i}^{(k-1)}) \right]. \quad (13)$$

The parameters $\Theta^{(k)}$ are estimated via the EM algorithm for truncated data with the estimation steps detailed in [7] and [8]. After convergence of the EM algorithm, at step k , the new values for $l_{x_i}^{(k)}$, $l_{y_i}^{(k)}$, and $\eta_i^{(k)}$, are calculated by

$$\begin{bmatrix} (l_{x_i}^{(k)})^2 & 0 \\ 0 & (l_{y_i}^{(k)})^2 \end{bmatrix} = (\hat{\Psi}_i^{(k)})^T \Sigma_i^{(k)} \hat{\Psi}_i^{(k)} - 2\hat{B} \quad (14)$$

and

$$\eta_i^{(k)} = \frac{\alpha_i^{(k)} \cdot (l_{x_i}^{(k)} \cdot l_{y_i}^{(k)})^{-1}}{\sum_j \alpha_j^{(k)} \cdot (l_{x_j}^{(k)} \cdot l_{y_j}^{(k)})^{-1}} \quad (15)$$

under the constraint $\sum_j \eta_j = 1$, and where \hat{B} is the diagonal matrix of estimated imaging PSF correlation lengths and $\hat{\Psi}_i^{(k)}$ is found via singular value decomposition of $\Sigma_i^{(k)}$. Equations (12) and (13) are then updated with new values for $f(\eta_i, l_{x_i}, l_{y_i})^{(k)}$ and $\Theta^{(k)}$. If the new estimate of the normalized ACF, $\hat{R}_{I_N}^{(k)}$ is approximately equal to the previous estimate, $\hat{R}_{I_N}^{(k-1)}$, the algorithm terminates. Otherwise the parameter set $\Theta^{(k+1)}$ is updated via the EM algorithm in another iteration. The algorithm iterates between updating Θ and \hat{R}_{I_N} until convergence. Upon convergence the estimates \hat{l}_{x_i} , \hat{l}_{y_i} , and $\hat{\eta}_i$, $i = 1, \dots, M$, are recovered via Equations (14)-(15). Using Equation (4) the variable $\hat{\theta}_i$ is recovered by

$$\hat{\theta}_i = \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{\hat{\Psi}_i(1, 2)}{\hat{\Psi}_i(1, 1)} \right), \quad (16)$$

where $\hat{\Psi}_i(m, n)$ is the element on the m -th row and n -th column of matrix $\hat{\Psi}_i$.

The ACF parameters found using the above parameter estimation technique describe the texture in terms of its correlation lengths in the x and y directions, orientation, and periodicity by the variables l_{x_i} , l_{y_i} , θ_i , and μ_{x_i} , μ_{y_i} respectively. Using the intensity ACF parameter estimation algorithm defined in previous work and the modifications explained above, a version of the algorithm was coded and fit to the rock (top), seagrass (middle), and ripple (bottom) textures in the left column of Figure 2. The results of the model fits to the estimated ACFs in the center column are depicted in the right column. The model used five components, three zero-mean components and one pair of nonzero-mean components. Parameters from this model and two other models will be used in the next section as features for an unsupervised SAS image segmentation algorithm.

Fig. 2: ACF model fit of rock (top), seagrass (middle), and ripple (bottom) seabed textures. The estimated ACFs, \hat{R}_I , are shown in the center column. The model fits using five mixture components, three zero-mean and two nonzero-mean, are shown in the right column.

III. SAS IMAGE SEGMENTATION USING INTENSITY ACF, WAVELET, AND HARALICK FEATURES

The ACF texture model feature set, a biorthogonal wavelet feature set, and a subset of the Haralick features [14] were used as input into an unsupervised multi-class k -means [15, Ch. 10, pp. 526-527] SAS image segmentation algorithm and the results of the three feature sets were compared. A set of 40 high-resolution 1000×1000 labeled SAS images containing distinct textures of sand, rock, small ripple (period ~ 20 -25 spatial samples), and large ripple (period ~ 45 -60 spatial samples) were used to test the segmentation algorithms. A texture label was assigned to each 25×25 pixel block in the original image resulting in a total of 64000 labeled texture samples for all 40 images. The breakdown of numbers of texture samples by class are as follows: 37553 sand samples, 8184 rock samples, 2190 small ripple samples, and 16073 large ripple samples. In all three tests, the feature vectors were combined into one large test set for the 40 images and were segmented together, i.e. a multi-image segmentation task.

Segmentation was carried out in two stages. In the first stage, the estimated shape parameter ν found using Raghavan's method [10] was used to differentiate between sand and nonsand textures in a k -means algorithm with $k = 2$. In the second stage, segmented nonsand textures were further segmented using k -means, $k = 3$, into rock, small sand ripple, and large sand ripple classes using the ACF, wavelet, and

Haralick features respectively. To normalize the relative scale of features within each feature extraction algorithm, the feature inputs to the k -means algorithm were first scaled to have zero-mean and unit variance. A description of the feature sets are detailed in the following subsections.

A. ACF Texture Features

Segmentation features for SAS images can be extracted using the parameters of the intensity ACF model presented in Section II. However, the number of components in the model must be defined prior to estimating the parameters, and it must be decided which, if any, of the components have a nonzero mean. Recent work [8] has shown that a four-component model with paired nonzero-mean components and two zero-mean components produces good segmentations on a variety of seabed textures. A feature vector \mathbf{f} of 10 elements comprising the mixture component correlation lengths, mixing parameters, and nonzero component means was constructed based on these findings, where

$$\mathbf{f} = \left\{ l_{x_1}, l_{x_2}, l_{x_3}, l_{y_1}, l_{y_2}, l_{y_3}, \alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_3, \sqrt{\mu_{x_1}^2 + \mu_{y_1}^2} \right\}. \quad (17)$$

The features were extracted from overlapping 200×200 pixel blocks in the original intensity image, assigning a feature vector to each 25×25 pixel block.

B. Biorthogonal Wavelet Features

A recent approach to multi-class unsupervised seabed segmentation uses biorthogonal wavelet transform coefficients [16, Ch. 7, pp. 266-272] to separate ripple, rock, and sand classes in SAS imagery [2]. Using the approach of [2] a wavelet feature vector of 16 elements was formed for overlapping windows of size 200×200 , by performing a five scale wavelet decomposition of the window using the MATLAB® function “dwt2” for the “bior1.3” wavelet family, and storing the root-mean square value of each wavelet scale as an element in the feature vector. Window size was chosen so that at least one period of the largest ripple would be captured in the decomposition.

C. Haralick Features

A well-known set of textural descriptors derived from the gray-level co-occurrence (GLCM) matrix is the Haralick feature set [14]. In this feature extraction approach, parameterized GLCMs are calculated for quantized windows of image textures and stored as elements in a feature vector. In [3], Haralick feature maps were used as inputs to a level-set segmentation algorithm for vector-valued images. Using the same GLCM parameters as in [3], a feature vector was created for overlapping 200×200 windows by calculating the GLCM for orientations of $0^\circ, -90^\circ, 45^\circ, -45^\circ$, interpixel distance 2, and 32-bit quantization of the original gray-scale image. Each feature vector contained 28 elements corresponding to four orientations of the *energy*, *contrast*, *correlation*, *entropy*, *homogeneity*, *cluster shade*, and *cluster prominence* values calculated from the GLCMs.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Table I summarizes the average correct segmentation results for 1000 random initializations of the k -means segmentation algorithm for the three feature sets plus or minus one standard deviation. Tables II - IV depict the mean confusion matrices for each of the feature vector configurations. Using this particular segmentation approach, the four-component ACF model feature vector yields superior segmentation results over segmentation using wavelet and Haralick features. However, this particular segmentation approach assumes that the three texture class are unimodal or well-clustered in feature space, and the larger the intercluster distance the better the segmentation results in the final label assignment.

To better understand the discriminatory ability and modality of each feature set in a supervised classification setting, another experiment was conducted using label assignment based on a simple k -nearest neighbor algorithm that assigns class labels by majority vote within a feature cluster. In this second experiment a k -means algorithm for values of $k = \{3, 6, 10, 15, 20, 30, 50, 100\}$ ran on each feature set, excluding any misclassified sand samples. The final rock, small ripple, or large ripple label for each texture sample was based on the majority class that occupied the same cluster and normalized for prior class probability so that texture classes with fewer samples have the same “vote” as texture classes with large numbers of samples. This second experiment infers how well each feature set could discriminate between classes for a given classifier complexity denoted by the number k in the k -means algorithm.

TABLE I: SAS Image Segmentation Results (in Pct. Correct)

Model Type	Sand	Rock	Small Ripple	Large Ripple
Haralick	92.9%	30.9 ± 19.7%	75.8 ± 21.8%	45.4 ± 6.2%
Wavelet	92.9%	45.4 ± 9.4%	27.8 ± 7.1%	33.5 ± 5.4%
ACF	92.9%	57.0 ± 6.9%	72.4 ± 4.8%	77.3 ± 0.3%

TABLE II: Confusion Matrix for Four-Component Model Segmentation Results

Label	Segmentation Results			
	Sand	Rock	Small Ripple	Large Ripple
Sand	92.9%	3.0 ± 0.5%	1.8 ± 0.6%	2.2 ± 0.1%
Rock	13.7%	57.0 ± 6.9%	23.8 ± 7.5%	5.5 ± 0.6%
Small Ripple	4.5%	22.6 ± 4.8%	72.4 ± 4.8%	0.6 ± 0.0%
Large Ripple	17.0%	0.2 ± 0.0%	5.5 ± 0.3%	77.3 ± 0.3%

In the second experiment, the k -means algorithm was randomly initialized 100 times for each k and the correct classification rate recorded. Figures 3 (a)-(d) depict the mean results for each feature set by texture class and averaged overall textures. The errorbars in the plots represent plus or minus one standard deviation. For small k the ACF texture model

Fig. 3: Error bar plots of texture classification rates using the three feature sets on 100 instantiations of the k -means algorithm at various values of k for (a) rock, (b) small ripple, and (c) large ripple textures. The averaged results are depicted in plot (d). The extremes of each error bar represents one standard deviation.

features provide good discriminatory information for the ripple textures, but performs poorly on rocky textures. The Haralick features underperform in segmenting the large ripple textures but segment the rock and small ripple textures better than the ACF and wavelet features for small values of k . The wavelet features segment all classes fairly well for $k > 20$, suggesting that all textures described by these features are highly multimodal. On average, the ACF model features perform well for $k < 30$ suggesting that this approach to feature extraction leads to simpler expressions of the data in feature space (fewer

clusters or modes) and requires less classifier complexity.

V. CONCLUSION

This paper presents a SAS image seabed texture feature extraction method based on estimating parameters from an autocorrelation function mixture model. This model describes seabed textures using orientation, correlation length, and periodicity features and can differentiate sand, rock, and ripple textures. An unsupervised multi-class segmentation approach using the k -means algorithm was used to segment rock,

TABLE III: Confusion Matrix for Biorthogonal Wavelet Segmentation Results

Label	Segmentation Results			
	Sand	Rock	Small Ripple	Large Ripple
Sand	92.9%	3.2 ± 0.0%	2.4 ± 0.7%	1.5 ± 0.7%
Rock	13.7%	45.4 ± 9.4%	19.5 ± 5.6%	21.4 ± 15.0%
Small Ripple	4.5%	42.8 ± 12.6%	27.8 ± 7.1%	24.8 ± 19.7%
Large Ripple	17.0%	33.0 ± 4.3%	16.6 ± 9.7%	33.5 ± 5.4%

TABLE IV: Confusion Matrix for Haralick Subset Segmentation Results

Label	Segmentation Results			
	Sand	Rock	Small Ripple	Large Ripple
Sand	92.9%	1.5 ± 0.3%	4.1 ± 0.4%	1.5 ± 0.1%
Rock	13.7%	30.9 ± 19.7%	37.9 ± 20.6%	17.6 ± 2.0%
Small Ripple	4.5%	18.7 ± 22.5%	75.8 ± 21.8%	1.0 ± 0.7%
Large Ripple	17.0%	28.9 ± 8.8%	8.8 ± 3.6%	45.4 ± 6.2%

small ripple, and large ripple seabed textures from a set of 40 SAS images using the features derived from the ACF model. These segmentation results were then compared to two other recently proposed seabed texture feature sets based on wavelet coefficients and Haralick features, respectively. In the first experiment, the ACF model features produced better segmentation results than the other features sets when the k -means algorithm assumed the number of modes or clusters was equal to the number of classes. A second experiment was conducted to calculate the complexity of the feature spaces created by the three feature extraction methods. For classifiers of low complexity, the ACF model features produced better segmentations than the features based on wavelet coefficients and Haralick features. As classifier complexity increased, the wavelet coefficient and Haralick features produced slightly better or equal segmentation results, inferring that the feature spaces from these competing feature extraction techniques are highly multimodal.

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